

Published as:

Sophie Elixhauser, Zofia Boni, Nataša Gregorič Bon, Urša Kanjir, Alexandra Meyer, Frank Muttenter, Mareike Pampus, Zdenka Sokolíčková (2024) “Interdisciplinary, but how? Anthropological Perspectives from Collaborative Research on Climate and Environmental Change”, *Environmental Science & Policy*, Volume 151.103586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.103586>.

Abstract:

The aim of this perspective article is to rethink *how* anthropology can be involved in interdisciplinary research on climate and environmental change, considering wide-spread obstacles for successful collaboration and recommending best practices and collaborative attitudes. Using an inductive approach, we derive our conclusions from ethnographic vignettes presented in this article that stem from a variety of interdisciplinary projects. Anthropologists complement “big data” with “thick data”, which must not be overlooked if the global scientific goal is to have a sustainable and responsible local impact in communities facing environmental change. Anthropologists are used to working with uncertainty, qualified for shifting scales and perspectives, and, perhaps most importantly, pre-occupied with studying the human dimensions of environmental change. However, there are still many practical, ontological and epistemological challenges concerning interdisciplinary research with an environmental focus. After outlining the most recent developments and literature on interdisciplinary research, we share our experience with integrating diverse forms of environmental knowledge including local and indigenous knowledge. Several key themes and suggestions emerge: a) establishment of a joint epistemological framework before the research phase; b) humility and respect for methodologies used by other disciplines, including time spent on studying these with colleagues of different disciplinary backgrounds; c) openness, creativity and flexibility to step out of one’s own disciplinary comfort zone; d) communication within the project team based on trust and without disciplinary hierarchies.

Keywords: climatic and environmental change; anthropology; interdisciplinarity; knowledge co-creation; good practices; collaboration

1. Introduction

In order to address the current climate and environmental crisis we need effective interdisciplinary research (e.g. Bhaskar et al., 2010; Hulme, 2011; Jäger et al., 2013; Palsson et al., 2013; Klenk & Meehal, 2015; Brondizio et al., 2016; Bruzzone et al., 2016; Obermeister, 2017; Maxwell, Hubbell & Eisenhauer, 2019; Eisenhauer et al., 2021) entailing conceptual and methodological collaborations among natural scientists, social scientists, and humanities scholars. Such collaborations, however, are difficult, messy and embedded in complex socio-political contexts (Bruzzone et al., 2016), all of which rarely make it into research outcomes (Schipper, Dubash & Mulugetta, 2021). There seems to be a scientific and political consensus that interdisciplinary research on climate and environmental change is needed (Agrawal et al., 2012; Barnes et al., 2013; Holm et al., 2013; Vaughn et al., 2021), but the question remains *how* exactly this could be done. The goal of this paper is to rethink how *anthropology* can be involved in interdisciplinary research on climate and environmental change and to give recommendations for successful collaboration integrating diverse forms of environmental knowledge.

The challenges of interdisciplinary research on climate and environmental change and potential solutions have been already widely studied. Ketler and Meehan (2015) set out three alternative models of knowledge co-production – triangulation, the multiple evidence-based approach, and scenario building – that would enrich environmental science. Brondizio et al. (2016) point out the need to address existing disciplinary tensions, strengths and barriers between distinct knowledge domains, and reframe how we conceptualize research questions. Nightingale (2016) highlights epistemological pluralism and the need to renounce proving methodologically which perspective is ‘better’, but rather acknowledge the value of probing contradictory results. Bruzzone et al. (2016) see interdisciplinary work not as a pre-condition but rather the result of the research process, which is more likely to happen if the study is more problem-driven than discipline-oriented. Integration—the act of bringing together or bridging perspectives—is considered key in knowledge co-production in inter- and transdisciplinary projects. However, it remains poorly understood and under-studied (Pohl et al., 2021). According to Eisenhauer et al. (2021), it is also necessary to distinguish between “integration” of social sciences in the research and the “application” of knowledge from the social sciences to research translation, while both are important.

Steger et al. (2021) identify specific skills and characteristics as beneficial for successful collaboration: flexibility, mutual respect and collaborative spirit; humility, trust and patience; persistence, interdisciplinary training and generosity. They also identify two main barriers for fruitful collaborations: insufficient time and unequal power dynamics. As tools to overcome the barriers, Steger et al. (2021) name time, shared goals, communication and strong leadership. In another study, weaving social science throughout the research process, strengthening social networks, and fostering interdisciplinary hubs are identified as key remedies (Maxwell, Hubbell & Eisenhauer, 2019). Drawing on interviews with researchers involved in interdisciplinary projects on environmental sustainability, Castán-Broto et al. (2009, p. 931) identified “the capacity to work collaboratively and an ethos of respect for other disciplines as essential characteristics of interdisciplinary researchers.”

Anthropologists are well equipped to participate in interdisciplinary projects for several reasons. First, they study the human dimensions of climate and environmental change, including the cultural values, political relations and historical contexts that shape respective knowledge and practices (Crate, 2011; de Wit & Haines, 2022; Krauß 2020; Latour, 2017; Meyer, 2022; Tsing et al., 2019; O’Reilly et al., 2020). As Maxwell, Hubbell and Eisenhauer, (2019, p. 103) put it, “place-based insights from ethnographic studies can help improve community uptake of science-based solutions by accounting for social and cultural factors”. Second, anthropologists are trained in long term research, self-reflexivity, working with complexity and uncertainty, and are experienced in co-creating knowledge and developing academic and non-academic collaborations.

This paper stems from the panel “Researching Climate/Environmental Change from a More-Than-Anthropology Perspective. The challenges and opportunities of interdisciplinary and multi-epistemic knowledge production”, held during the international conference Vienna Anthropology Days in September 2022, where the authors discussed interdisciplinary research challenges. The majority of the authors are scholars who in the current phases of our professional careers identify as anthropologists, and we all are or have been involved in collaborative projects dealing with climate and environmental change. To build the argument we present in this article, we reiterated our individual experiences in a collective dialogue, situating it within existing literature or related issues.

2. Challenges in interdisciplinary research

In this section we discuss some wide-spread challenges of interdisciplinary research by means of ethnographic vignettes showcasing respective experiences of the authors (for a description of the referenced projects, see the appendix).

During my ethnographic fieldwork in East Greenland, I was camping out with Inuit friends next to a glacier that started to calve in the middle of the night. We only just managed to leave the location; our boat could have easily become blocked by the ice for weeks. After this incident, I was told that the “ice is alive”, suggesting that my inappropriate laughter near the glacier may have provoked its moving. I learned that people’s lifeworlds – certainly in pre-Christian times and today still in some ways – are based on the animistic notion of a variety of living beings (human and non-human) that have agency and may harm people (Elixhauser 2018). This is hardly compatible with the scientific explanation of such events, for instance given by climatologists who refer to wind and water erosion and mass loss due to human-made climate change. (Elixhauser, Snow2Rain)

Ontological challenges may appear when working within contexts where local populations experience environmental changes in a categorically different way compared to explanations offered by natural sciences (e.g. Tsing et al., 2019; Viveiros de Castro, 2019).

During one of the first project meetings I joined, a natural scientist in the team made a remark about social scientists “just chatting“ with their research participants while for the project we need to efficiently fish out the stories of environmental change. “We don’t know each other’s research methods, which means we don’t respect them,“ I thought. Later in the project while working on our first joint publication, my expression “the data we created“ kept being corrected into “the data we collected“. But in anthropology, you don’t “collect data“ as if they were pebbles lying on the shore, ready to be picked. You create an atmosphere of trust and intimacy when people open up and share stories. That takes time and more than “chatting“. (Sokolíčková, SVALUR)

Epistemological challenges concern questions about what is knowledge and what qualifies as “data”, which might be answered differently by collaborators from different disciplines (Obermeister, 2017; Redclift, 1998; Roturier & Beau, 2022; Sokolíčková et al., 2023). Even

within one discipline we find different research traditions, and some anthropologists, for instance, speak of collecting data instead of (co-)creating them. Qualitative methods aim at learning about embodied and sensory experiences and subjective forms of knowing. Hence, qualitative research counts as producing knowledge in disciplines such as anthropology, whereas elsewhere these methods do not form part of the scientific repertoire as they are seen as “subjective”, which can lead to “science friction” (Edwards et al., 2011). Subjectivity, however, does not imply a lower scientific value as long as its repercussions, including the researcher's positionality, are properly reflected upon (Clifford and Marcus, 1986).

Such **methodological challenges** and presupposed **hierarchies of knowledge**, often manifesting in disciplinary prejudices, cause tensions and hinder scientific progress in projects. Collaborators with a different disciplinary training frequently expect anthropologists to use “exact procedures” and produce quantifiable outcomes (Maxwell, Hubbell & Eisenhauer, 2019). The quantifiable sciences tend to be perceived by the public, policy makers and within academia as the “better” or “real” sciences. As Schipper, Dubash and Mulugetta underline, “often numbers get prioritized over stories” (2021, p. 3). Also during fieldwork, misunderstandings about tasks, sources of data and responsibilities can emerge.

When the marine scientists noticed I classify fishing techniques and tools differently, reflecting the native fishers' own know-how, they got angry. They argued they hadn't hired an anthropologist to study fishing techniques and tools and instead of criticizing them I should rather study the "local culture". Rituals and village folklore, local trade and markets... whatever, but not fishing techniques already “taken care of” by the natural scientists. It resulted in an unresolvable conflict. They insisted on using their typology as a misleading basis for quantification of fishing effort while trying to prevent me from pursuing my own ethnographic research since my results might ultimately disprove theirs. (Muttenger, CORECRAB)

At the same time, there is a tendency to regard the natural or empirical sciences as stuffy, hard in their mind-set, following only numbers that occur in empirical investigation relying on testability and replicability. We argue that the dichotomy of “objective” data and more “subjective” interpretative approaches needs to be overcome. Obermeister (2017, p. 85) claims that “acknowledging the importance of internal epistemological differences, both in research and practice, may help distinguish deeper philosophical and political points of contention from less problematic procedural concerns, which may be more capable of

resolution.” Quantitative and qualitative methods from natural and social sciences and the humanities should be understood as complementary, a fruitful combination of what we call “big data” and “thick data” (Gregorič Bon et al., 2022; Kanjir et al., 2022).

Not only is this hierarchy embedded in the mainstream academic system, but also in the logic of state bureaucracies and global environmental policy institutions. Oftentimes, only the natural scientific explanations form the basis for political decisions, such as environmental policy measures leading to counterproductive consequences (e.g. establishment of protected areas overriding the needs of the inhabitants, see West & Brockington, 2006). When anthropologists participate in the discussion they are often critical towards the managerial stance of environmentalist bureaucrats. They may even be perceived as a threat to the institutional interests by promoting inclusive methodologies complicating the institution's task through “uncomfortable knowledge“ (Schipper, Dubash & Mulugetta, 2021, p. 7).

There are also **structural challenges** related to disciplinary divisions, translating into practical issues, such as short lifespan of research projects and funding patterns (Arpin et al., 2023; König & Gorman, 2017). Funding bodies tend to favor large-scale research projects with internal architectures that resemble faculties and departments of a university or ministries of a state bureaucracy. Anthropologists and their work are often tokenized, added as a cherry on top to the research project with their “illustrative quotes” from “the locals” or as mediators between local communities and scientists, rather than included as partners with equally valid findings. Anthropological research is sometimes reduced to adding rather essentializing traditional ecological knowledge to IPCC reports and the like (Singleton et al., 2021). In addition, the funding scheme logistics limits anthropological research. Usually the respective setup of a project and chronological research steps do not allow for a long term inductive approach common in anthropology, including adaptation or change of research questions throughout the process. The same can be said about possibilities for true co-creation with local stake- and right-holders (Doering et al., 2022).

Efforts to overcome some of the discussed problems include risks such as dedicating large amounts of time to learning about the other disciplines’ approaches. This time might be missed later on in the project cycle for fulfilling one’s own disciplinary requirements, for instance in terms of writing articles for preferably high ranked journals (Castán Broto, Gislason & Ehlers, 2009). If the researchers give precedence to the requirements of their own

discipline (e.g. a theoretical contribution), the project outputs might become less interdisciplinary and applied (cf. Elixhauser, 2006, p. 92).

3. Good Practices and Collaborative Attitudes

Good practices and collaborative attitudes, often interrelated, can be used as practical tools to overcome the manifold challenges of interdisciplinary encounters.

Already in the first phases of our interdisciplinary research intersecting anthropology, geography and remote sensing on the riverine environment of Vjosa (Albania), we found that we depart from different disciplinary conceptualizations of the key phenomena under study. Take “landscape”, defined as two opposed domains – people and pixels. We spent a great deal of time discussing our methods for collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and monitoring different datasets. One dataset, people, is largely grasped through participant observation, thick description, and in-depth, often repeated conversations. Pixels are based on numerical, quantitative data collected and monitored by satellite systems orbiting the Earth surface, translating the physical features of a geographic area into pixels. This data is later analyzed and mapped using various algorithms. (Gregorič Bon, Experiencing Water)

Long-term collaboration is essential in interdisciplinary research (Steger et al., 2021). To reflect on particular bodies of knowledge, it is important for researchers to read scholarly articles from the other disciplines to develop shared knowledge. Discussing key research concepts and their meanings among participating disciplines might contribute to avoiding epistemological dissonances and theoretical misinterpretations (Bruzzone et al. 2016). Brainstorming sessions and joint fieldwork are important here, as they help to disentangle key phenomena and decipher different meanings of the data. Researchers need time to discuss these differences as well as similarities, entanglements, and ruptures in the way they read, analyze, and interpret different data sets.

Reflexivity towards one's own and other disciplinary epistemologies and methods is an important component of interdisciplinary research. Anthropological methods are often based on returning to and revising the original research question. Almost the opposite is true in the natural and technical sciences, which rely largely on deduction from research data, replicability, and formulating hypotheses in advance that are either confirmed or rejected through a research process. In this sense, researchers should be open to stepping out of their

disciplinary “comfort zones” (Castán Broto, Gislason & Ehlers, 2009; Kontou et al., 2022) and openly but responsibly seek to understand other disciplinary methodologies, data analysis and conceptualizations. Above all, the research process, whether interdisciplinary or disciplinary, is a relational process.

After walking all day along the canyon of the Vjosa River tributary, swimming in its cold water we were immersed by its beauty and enriched by the passionate explanations of a geographer about the complex geomorphological features we encountered during our hike. Afterwards, we drove to a restaurant and on the way there, the geographer suddenly asked to stop the car. We walked about 400 meters across the meadow to the place where the eroded riverbed showed many colors of soil and gravel. After explaining about the sediments clearly visible in the riverbed, which showed the course of the river over the years, I remarked that these sediments could also denote the memory of the river. The geographer paused for a moment and said, "Well, you could call it that, but in geography, especially geomorphology, we do not use that word." Although the geographer could not quite comprehend my comment, he subtly grasped its point and resonated with it. (Gregorič Bon, Experiencing Water)

Resonance is based on disciplinary openness, generosity, and trust, grounded in both professional and personal relationships. It depends on an ethic of sharing ideas, research data, plans, as well as doubts and disagreements about research phenomena. It is thus "a way of listening, hearing, responding to subtleties (rather than agreeing over concepts)" (Petrović-Šteger, 2016, p. 47). It is necessary to develop an understanding both at the intellectual and personal level (Castán Broto, Gislason & Ehlers, 2009). Personal contact is thus crucial here. This is especially important today, as many interdisciplinary teams rely largely on virtual meetings due to their geographic distance. Sharing subtle experiences, often based on physical relationships, is important to interdisciplinarity.

Equality across and between disciplines, overcoming knowledge hierarchies, is another important component of interdisciplinary collaboration. It is based on respect, disciplinary and epistemic humility: knowing what you don't know and knowing what you *can't* know, while other disciplines might. As noted by Holm et al. (2013, p. 26), the human and social sciences are often relegated to an “auxiliary, advisory, and essentially non-scientific status”, and part of the “normative” or “strategic” questions (while the analytical questions are related to the natural sciences). In contrast, Viveiros de Castro (2019) argued for an “ontological anarchy”

by which different bodies of knowledge, such as environmental models, local ways of knowing, anthropological or other discipline's scientific knowledge, etc. are juxtaposed on equal terms (cf. Tsing et al., 2019). Such an approach assumes that anthropological research should not be tokenized, and treated as just an illustration of other kinds of data, but rather as equally valid data in and of itself. To deal with this aspect in a respectful manner, Schnegg argues that multiple worlds may coexist and that it is crucial “to change the focus from detecting who's got it right (in the sense of a correspondence theory of truth) to evaluating who has a more *viable* answer to the questions at stake” (2021, p. 270).

At the start of our interdisciplinary research on embodying climate change and urban heat we discussed the main research concepts. One of them was heat. When I started talking about the difficulties with understanding how people experience urban heat during the summer, how difficult to grasp and study it might be because it is so invisible, a physicist interrupted me: “What are you saying? Of course we know what heat is. It is a form of energy transfer, and it is clearly defined”. Then we found out that in Warsaw the summer heat starts for some people already at 25°C, while official heatwave alerts start only above 30°C, and the thresholds for climate scientists are even higher. Heat(wave) is a different thing depending on the perspective. (Boni, EmCliC)

A fruitful avenue for interdisciplinary collaboration is to let researchers from different disciplines examine various aspects of the same phenomenon, depending on the strengths of each and the specific research questions (Brondizio et al., 2016). This leads us to some final points about **co-creation**. Anthropologists are well trained in documenting and analyzing different worldviews and epistemologies. Instead of judging different perspectives, they aim at understanding them, declining claims about “objective” systems of knowledge production. A non-hierarchical attitude is essential in interdisciplinary projects where different scientific approaches should be treated as equal, as each is providing insights into different aspects of the phenomena in question. This attitude is also the basic premise for co-creating research with indigenous or non-indigenous knowledge- and rightsholders. As described in the vignette above, anthropologists co-create knowledge with their research partners, where all should be treated equally throughout the research process. This attitude is also important (yet less common) for colleagues from the natural sciences, who are called on collaborating with local and indigenous rightsholders and including their interests in the research they conduct in their homelands (Doering et al., 2022).

4. Conclusion

In our effort to rethink how anthropology can be involved in interdisciplinary research on climate and environmental change, we sketched wide-spread challenges and gave recommendations for successful collaboration.

Anthropologists should be involved in the project planning and design right from the start instead of adding them at a later point when the project is already designed. To do truly interdisciplinary research, different theoretical perspectives, ways of knowing and methods should be incorporated from the beginning. However, to learn about and from the other disciplines, to overcome prejudices and to establish a joint epistemological framework requires time. It is of utmost importance to understand quantitative and qualitative methods as complementary, while considering their different temporal affordances. For doing so, widespread disciplinary hierarchies both within the public and academic sphere have to be challenged. Working in interdisciplinary teams requires a jargon-free language, beneficial also for co-creative research endeavors and science communication with the public. Collaborative attitudes facilitate interdisciplinary projects. These include reflexivity, readiness to step out of one's disciplinary comfort zone, resonance and trust in research teams on both personal and disciplinary levels.

There is a tendency to reduce anthropologists to studying local knowledge added on top of other quantifiable systems of knowledge or to the role of mediators between natural scientists and local communities. We argue that in the field of global environmental change, anthropology can do more than just that.

References

- Agrawal, A., Lemos, M., Orlove, B., Ribot, J. (2012) Cool heads for a hot world — social sciences under a changing sky. *Global Environmental Change* 22, 329–331. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2012.02.003>
- Arpin, I., Likhacheva, K., Bretagnolle, V. (2023). Organising inter- and transdisciplinary research in practice. The case of the meta-organisation French LTSER platforms. *Environmental Science and Policy* 144, 43–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.03.009>
- Barnes, J., Dove, M., Lahsen, M., Mathews, A., McElwee, P., McIntosh, R., Moore, R., O'Reilly, J., Orlove, B., Puri, R., Weisse, H., Yager, K. (2013) Contribution of anthropology to the study of climate change. *Nature Climate Change* 3, 541–544. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1775>
- Bhaskar, R., Frank, C., Høyer, K.G., Naess, P., Parker, J. (Eds.) (2010) *Interdisciplinarity and climate change: transforming knowledge and practice for our global future*. Routledge, London. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203855317>
- Brondizio, E., O'Brien, K., Bai, X., Biermann, F., Steffen, W., Berkhout, F., Cudennec, Ch., Lemos, M.C., Wolfe, A., Palma-Oliveira, J., Chen, Ch.-T.A. (2016) Re-conceptualizing the anthropocene: a call for collaboration. *Global Environmental Change* 39, 318–327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.02.006>
- Bruzzone, S., Larrue, C., Rijswick, M. van, Wiering, M., Crabbé, A. (2016) Constructing collaborative communities of researchers in the environmental domain. A case study of interdisciplinary research between legal scholars and policy analysts. *Environmental Science and Policy* 64, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2016.05.014>
- Castán Broto, V., Gislason, M., Ehlers, M.-H. (2009) Practising interdisciplinarity in the interplay between disciplines: experiences of established researchers. *Environmental Science and Policy* 12(7), 922–933. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2009.04.005>
- Castree, N., Adams, W., Barry, J., Brockington, D., Büscher, B., Corbera, E., Demeritt, D., Duffy, R., Felt, U., Neves, K., Pellizzoni, L., Rigby, K., Robbins, P., Robin, L., Rose, D.B., Ross, A., Schlosberg, D., Sörlin, S., West, P., Whitehead, M., Wynne, B. (2014) Changing the intellectual climate. *Nature Climate Change* 4, 763–768. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2339>
- Clifford, J., Marcus, G. (Ed.) (1986) *Writing culture: The poetics and politics of ethnography*. Berkeley, University of California Press.
- Crate, S. A. (2011) Climate and culture: anthropology in the era of contemporary climate change. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 40, 175–194. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.anthro.012809.104925>
- Cundill, G., Roux, D. J., Parker, J. N. (2015) Nurturing communities of practice for transdisciplinary research. *Ecology and Society* 20(2), 22. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-07580-200222>
- de Wit, S., Haines, S. (2022) Climate change reception studies in anthropology. *WIREs Climate Change* 13, e742. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.742>

- Doering, N.N., Dudeck, S., Elverum, S., Fisher, C., Henriksen, J. E., Herrmann, T.M., Kramvig, B., Laptander, R., Milton, J., Omma, E. M., Saxinger, G., Scheepstra, A.J.M., Wilson, K. (2022) Improving the relationships between indigenous rights holders and researchers in the arctic: an invitation for change in funding and collaboration. *Environmental Research Letters* 17(6). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac72b5>
- Edwards P.N., Mayernik M.S., Batcheller A.L., Bowker G.C., Borgman C.L. (2011) Science friction: Data, metadata, and collaboration. *Social Studies of Science* 41(5), 667–90. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312711413314>
- Eisenhauer, E., Williams, K. C., Margeson, K., Paczuski, S., Hano, M. C., Mulvaney, K. (2021) Advancing translational research in environmental science: the role and impact of social sciences. *Environmental Science and Policy* 120, 165–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.03.010>
- Elixhauser, S. (2006) *Ethik in der angewandten Ethnologie: Eine Feldforschung zum Tourismus auf den Philippinen [Ethics in applied anthropology: Field research on tourism in the Philippines]*. Norderstedt, BoD.
- Elixhauser, S. (2018) *Negotiating personal autonomy: Communication and personhood in East Greenland*. London, New York, Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315157832>
- Geertz, C. (1973) *The interpretation of cultures: Selected essays*. New York, Basic Books.
- Gregorič Bon, N., Stančič, L., Kanjir, U. (2022) Vjosa riverine environments: Approaching dynamic continuity. *Anthropological Notebooks* 28(3), 37–73. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7463519>
- Holm, P., Goodsite, M. E., Cloetingh, S., Agnoletti, M., Moldan, B., Lang, D. J., Leemans, R., Oerstroem Moeller, J., Pardo Buendía, M., Pohl, W., Scholz, R. W., Sors, A., Vanheusden, B., Yusoff, K., Zondervan, R. (2013) Collaboration between the natural, social and human sciences in Global Change Research. *Environmental Science & Policy* 28, 25-35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.11.010>
- Hulme, M. (2011) Meet the humanities. *Nature Climate Change* 1, 177–179. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1150>
- Jäger, J., Holm, P., O'Brien, K., Palsson, G., Pahl-Wostl, C., Chabay, I., Reams, J. (2013) Editorial: Responses to environmental and societal challenges for our unstable earth. *Environmental Science & Policy* 28, 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2013.01.001>
- Kanjir, U., Gregorič Bon, N., Stančič, L., Josipovič, D. (2022) *Riverine environments: Following Mura and Vjosa = Rečna okolja: s tokovi Mure in Vjose = Mjediset lumore: përgjatë Murës dhe Vjosës*. Ljubljana, Institute of Anthropological and Spatial Studies, ZRC SAZU. <https://riverchange.zrc-sazu.si/>
- Klenk, N., Meehan, K. (2015) Climate change and transdisciplinary science: Problematizing the integration imperative. *Environmental Science & Policy* 54, 160-167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.05.017>
- Knox, H. (2020) *Thinking like a climate: governing a city in times of environmental change*. Durham, Duke University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9781478012405>

- König, T., Gorman, M. (2017) “The challenge of funding interdisciplinary research: a look inside public research funding agencies”. In *The Oxford Handbook of Interdisciplinarity*, ed. R. Frodeman, pp. 513–524. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198733522.013.41>
- Kontou, D.-M., Ferloni, G., Seddon L. (2022) “Interdisciplinary knowledge production of environmental changes in the Arctic: A geographers’ perspective”. Presentation at Vienna Anthropology Days 2022, Sept 26-29, 2022, Vienna.
- Krauß, W., Bremer, S. (2020) The role of place-based narratives of change in climate risk governance. *Climate Risk Management* 28, 100221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2020.100221>
- Latour, B. (2017) „Anthropology at the time of the Anthropocene: a personal view of what Is to be studied“. In *The Anthropology of Sustainability*, ed. M. Brightman, J. Lewis, pp. 35–49. New York, Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-56636-2_2
- Maxwell, K., Hubbell, B., Eisenhauer, E. (2019) Institutional insights on integrating social and environmental science for solutions-driven research. *Environmental Science and Policy* 101, 97–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.08.003>
- Meyer, A. C. 2022. Physical and feasible: climate change adaptation in Longyearbyen, Svalbard. *Polar Record* 58: e29. <http://doi.org/10.1017/s0032247422000079>
- Nightingale, A. J. (2016) Adaptive scholarship and situated knowledges? Hybrid methodologies and plural epistemologies in climate change adaptation research. *Area* 48 (1), 41–47. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24812193>
- Obermeister, N. (2017) From dichotomy to duality: Addressing interdisciplinary epistemological barriers to inclusive knowledge governance in global environmental assessments. *Environmental Science and Policy* 68, 80–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2016.11.010>
- O'Reilly, J., Isenhour, C., McElwee, P., Orlove, B. (2020) Climate change: Expanding anthropological possibilities. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 49, 13–29. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-010220-043113>
- Palsson, G., Szerszynski, B., Sörlin, S., Marks, J., Avril, B., Crumley, C., Hackmann, H., Holm, P., Ingram, J., Kirman, A., Pardo Buendía, M., Weehuizen, R. (2013) Reconceptualizing the ‘Anthropos’ in the Anthropocene: Integrating the social sciences and humanities in global environmental change research. *Environmental Science and Policy* 28, 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.11.004>
- Petrović-Šteger, M. (2016) On resonance: A brief ethnography of collaboration in the social sciences. *ISRF Bulletin* 10 (Discovery & Recognition), 39–47.
- Pohl, C., Thompson Klein, J., Hoffmann, S., Mitchell, C., Fam, D. (2021). Conceptualising transdisciplinary integration as a multidimensional interactive process. *Environmental Science and Policy* 118, 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.12.005>
- Redclift, M. (1998) Dances with wolves? Interdisciplinary research on the global environment. *Global Environmental Change* 8 (3), 177–182. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780\(98\)00020-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780(98)00020-X)

- Roturier, S., Beau, R. (2022) Digital technologies and ILK in the Arctic: In search of epistemological pluralism. *Environmental Science and Policy* 133, 164–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.03.025>
- Schipper, E.L.F., Dubash, N.K., Mulugetta, Y. (2021) Climate change research and the search for solutions: Rethinking interdisciplinarity. *Climatic Change* 168(18). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-021-03237-3>
- Schnegg, M. (2021) Ontologies of climate change: Reconciling indigenous and scientific explanations for the lack of rain in Namibia. *American Ethnologist* 48, 260–273. <https://doi.org/10.1111/amet.13028>
- Steger, C., Klein, J.A., Reid, R.S., Lavorel, S., Tucker, C., Hopping, K.A., Marchant, R., Teel, T., Cuni-Sanchez, A., Dorji, T., Greenwood, G., Huber, R., Kassam, K.-A., Kreuer, D., Nolin, A., Russell, A., Sharp, J.L., Šmid Hribar, M., Thorn, J.P.R., Grant, G., Mahdi, M., Moreno, M., Waiswa, D. (2021) Science with society: Evidence-based guidance for best practices in environmental transdisciplinary work. *Global Environmental Change* 68, 102240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102240>
- Singleton, B.E., Gillette, M.B., Burman, A., Green, C. (2021) Toward productive complicity: Applying ‘traditional ecological knowledge’ in environmental science. *The Anthropocene Review* 0(0), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20530196211057026>
- Sokolíčková, Z., Ramírez Hincapié, E., Zhang, J., Lennert, A. E., Löf, A., van der Wal, R. (2023) Waters that matter: How human-environment relations are changing in high-Arctic Svalbard. *Anthropological Notebooks* 28(3), 74-109. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7463504>
- Tsing, A.L., Mathews, A.S., Bubandt, N. (2019) Patchy Anthropocene: Landscape structure, multispecies history, and the retooling of anthropology. *Current Anthropology* 60 (S20): S186–97. <https://doi.org/10.1086/703391>
- Vaughn, S.E., Guarasci, B., Moore, A. (2021) Intersectional ecologies: Reimagining anthropology and environment. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 50, 275–290. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-101819-110241>
- Viveiros de Castro, E. (2019) On models and examples: Engineers and bricoleurs in the Anthropocene. *Current Anthropology* 60 (S20): S296–S308. <https://doi.org/10.1086/702787>
- West, P., Brockington, D. (2006) An anthropological perspective on some unexpected consequences of protected areas. *Conservation Biology* 20(3), 609–616. <https://conbio.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2006.00432.x>

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Peter Schweitzer for comments on an earlier draft of the paper. We also thank the active audience at VANDA conference 2022 in Vienna who attended and exchanged ideas throughout our workshop entitled, “Researching climate/environmental change from a more-than-anthropology perspective: The challenges and opportunities of interdisciplinary and multi-epistemic knowledge production.” We acknowledge funding from the Austrian Academy of Sciences (project Snow2Rain), Austria’s Agency for Education and Internationalisation OeAD Sparkling Science (project Snow2School), the Belmont Forum (project SVALUR), the ERC (project InfraNorth, no. 885646), EU Horizon 2020 (project Nunataryuk, no. 773421), the EEA grants operated by the Polish National Science Centre (2019/35/J/HS6/03992, project EmCliC), and the Slovenian Research Agency (J6-4611, P-0079).

Appendix

CORECRAB, was a multidisciplinary research project on economic and ecological change in the mangrove crab fisheries of Madagascar, running from 2020 to 2023. It included researchers from fishery ecology, social economy and one anthropologist. The project combined quantitative data collected by ecologists, a household survey and ethnographic findings in order to propose a diagnostic of ecological changes as well as the social dynamics involved. <http://corecrabe.ird.fr>

EO-Context - Contextualization of EO data for a deeper understanding of river environment changes in Southeast Europe (funded by ESA) and **Experiencing Water and Water Environments** (funded by the Slovenian Research Agency). Both projects ran almost in parallel between 2019-2022 and explored the multitude of entanglements between riverine landscapes and social worlds. <https://riverchange.zrc-sazu.si/>

EmCliC (Embodying Climate Change: Transdisciplinary Research on Urban Overheating), conducted in 2020-2024, brings together social anthropology, sociology, climate science, epidemiology, atmospheric physics and novel technology, to understand and demonstrate how people experience urban heat, and with that climate change, on a daily basis. The research project is funded from the EEA grants 2014–2021 under the Basic Research Programme operated by the Polish National Science Centre in cooperation with the Research Council of Norway (grant no 2019/35/J/HS6/03992). www.emclitic.com

Snow2Rain – From phase transition of precipitation to changing local livelihoods, emotions and affects in East Greenland (2020-2023). This research project is a collaboration between climatologists (University of Graz) and anthropologists (University of Vienna). It is aimed at understanding how environmental changes, in particular the transition from snow to rain, are influencing quality of life in the Tasiilaq region in East Greenland. The project is based on a combination of physical measurements and data from climate models and local expertise on this topic. <https://www.snow2rain.com>

SVALUR (Understanding Resilience and Long-Term Ecosystem Change in the High Arctic: Narrative-Based Analyses from Svalbard) is a research project funded by Belmont Forum as part of the call Resilience in a Rapidly Changing Arctic. Its time span is 2020–2023 and it aims at combining formal environmental monitoring with the knowledge and observations from people of all walks of life (such as scientists, technicians, long-term residents and tour guides) in Svalbard. <https://www.slu.se/svalur>